

ISBI 2025 - Proposal template for Call for Challenges

SUMMARY

Item 1: Title

a) Use the title to convey the essential information on the **challenge mission**.

Fetal Ultrasound Grand Challenge: Semi-Supervised Cervical Segmentation

b) Preferable, provide a short **acronym** of the challenge (if any).

FUGC25

Item 2: Abstract

Provide a **summary** of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Premature birth remains one of the leading causes of neonatal mortality in the U.S. and other developed nations, posing significant healthcare challenges. Despite numerous efforts, strategies to prevent preterm labor and birth have yielded only limited success. However, recent advancements have improved the ability to predict preterm birth, offering a crucial opportunity for early intervention. Among these advancements, ultrasound imaging of the uterine cervix has emerged as a key clinical tool in predicting spontaneous preterm labor and birth. Early identification of high-risk pregnancies enables healthcare professionals to focus obstetric and neonatal care on those most in need, improving outcomes.

From a biomedical perspective, transvaginal ultrasound is the preferred method for visualizing the cervix in most patients, offering detailed insight into cervical anatomy and structure. Accurate segmentation of ultrasound (US) images of the cervical muscles is essential for analyzing deep muscle structures, assessing their function, and monitoring treatment protocols tailored to individual patients.

From a technical standpoint, the manual annotation of cervical structures in transvaginal ultrasound images is labor-intensive and time-consuming, limiting the availability of large labeled datasets required for robust machine learning models. In response to this challenge, semisupervised learning approaches have shown potential by leveraging both labeled and unlabeled data, enabling the extraction of useful information from unannotated cases. This method could reduce the need for extensive manual annotation while maintaining accuracy, thus accelerating the development of automated cervical image segmentation systems. The envisioned impact of this challenge is twofold: improving clinical decision-making through more accessible and accurate diagnostic tools and advancing machine learning techniques for medical image analysis, particularly in resource-constrained environments.

We extend the MICCAI PSFHS 2023 Challenge and the MICCAI IUGC 2024 Challenge from fully supervised settings to a semi-supervised setting that focuses on how to use unlabeled data. Specifically, we provide a small number of labeled cases (50) and a large number of unlabeled cases (450) in the training set, 90 visible cases for validation, and 300 hidden cases for testing.

The FUGC25 challenge has three main features:

- (1) Task: we use a semi-supervised setting that focuses on how to use unlabeled data.
- (2) Dataset: we curate a large-scale and diverse ultrasound dataset, including 800+ images obtained with seven different ultrasound machines;
- (3) Evaluation measures: we not only focus on segmentation accuracy but also segmentation efficiency and resource consumption.

Item 3: Keywords

List the primary **keywords** that characterize the challenge.

Preterm birth, Cervix, Segmentation, fetal ultrasound, Semi-supervised learning

CHALLENGE ORGANIZATION

Item 4: Organizers

a) Provide information on the **organizing team** (names and affiliations).

Jieyun Bai, the University of Auckland, Auckland, New Zealand and Jinan University, Guangzhou, China
Ziduo Yang, Jinan University, Guangzhou, China
Md. Kamrul Hasan, Imperial College London, London, UK
Jie Gan, University of Sydney, Sydney, Australia
Zhuonan Liang, University of Sydney, Sydney, Australia
Weidong Cai, University of Sydney, Sydney, Australia
Tao Tan, Netherlands Cancer Institute (NKI), Amsterdam, The Netherlands and Macao Polytechnic University, Macao SAR, China
Jing Ye, Monash University Monash, Australia and Shanghai AI Laboratory, Shanghai, China
Mohammad Yaqub, Mohamed bin Zayed University, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates
Dong Ni, Shenzhen University, China
Saad Slimani, Ibn Rochd University Hospital, Hassan II University, Casablanca, Morocco
Benard Ohene-Botwe, Department of Radiography, School of Biomedical and Allied Health Sciences, College of Health Sciences, University of Ghana, Accra, Ghana
Campello Roman Victor Manuel, Artificial Intelligence in Medicine Lab (BCN-AIM), Barcelona, Spain
Karim Lekadir, Artificial Intelligence in Medicine Lab (BCN-AIM), Barcelona, Spain

b) Provide information on the **primary contact person**.

Jieyun Bai (jbai996@aucklanduni.ac.nz, baijieyun@jnu.edu.cn, jieyun.bai@ieee.org)

Item 5: Lifecycle type

Define the intended **submission cycle** of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place.

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed submission deadline
- Open call
- Repeated event with annual fixed submission deadline

One-time event with fixed submission deadline

Item 6: Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the **event** (e.g. conference) that is **associated** with the challenge (if any).

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b) Report the **platform** (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

grand-challenge.org (will setup once the proposal is accepted)

c) Provide the **URL** for the challenge website (if any).

None at this moment.

Item 7: Participation policies

a) Define the **allowed user interaction** of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the **usage of training data**. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

No additional data allowed.

c) Define the **participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes**. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard.

d) Define the **award policy**. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

We will provide a prize (cash and certificate) for the top 10 teams. Our two MICCAI challenges (i.e., PSFHS2023 and IUGC2024) were sponsored by Guangzhou Lian-Med Technologies Co., Ltd., who provided the prizes for the winning team, so we do not anticipate any issues sourcing prizes for 2025. Note: A prerequisite for receiving cash prizes and award certificates is that participants need to provide the source code give a presentation about their methods, as well as submit papers describing methods and results. The details of this will be announced on our challenge homepage at a later date.

e) Define the policy for **result announcement**.

Examples:

- Top three performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

All performance results will be made public, and the participants will be invited to participate in a challenge event to showcase their work.

f) Define the **publication policy**. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

Participating teams can also anyway publish their own results independently. We also intend to coordinate with the participating teams to submit a journal article summarizing the main results and conclusions drawn from the challenge.

Item 8: Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the **submission instructions**.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Submissions will be made via Docker container.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to **evaluate** their **algorithms before submitting** final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

We allow three successful submissions on the validation set (with pre-defined deadlines) and only once on the testing set.

Item 9: Challenge schedule

Provide a **timetable** for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

Challenge website running and registration open: 12/09/2024

Release of the dataset and starter code: 12/15/2024

Submission deadline: 03/01/2024

Release of final results (decisions): 03/15/2024

Challenge days (ISBI main conference): 04/14/2025-04/17/2025

Item 10: Ethics approval

Indicate whether **ethics approval** is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a **reference to the document** of the ethics approval (if available).

Our dataset was curated from public domains with the license permits. There is no patient information included. Thus, we do not need additional ethics approval.

Item 11: Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit **listing of the license** applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Answer: CC BY-NC-SA

Item 12: Code availability

a) Provide information on the **accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software** (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

Evaluation code will be made available with the training data.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the **accessibility of the participating teams' code**.

Top 10 teams should make their code publicly available. The remaining teams are encouraged to make their code publicly available.

Item 13: Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to **sponsoring/ funding** of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have **access to the test case labels** and when.

There are no conflicts of interest. Guangzhou Lian-Med Technologies Co., Ltd. is the principal sponsor of the challenge. Only the organizers and technical groups of the challenge have access to test case labels.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Item 14: Field(s) of application

State the **main field(s) of application** that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Research, CAD, Decision support

Item 15: Task category(ies)

State the **task category(ies)**.

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Segmentation

Item 16: Cohorts

We distinguish between the *target cohort* and the *challenge cohort*. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on *ex vivo* data obtained from a laparoscopic training

environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding gender or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the **target cohort**, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The target cohort consists of pregnant women required to screen preterm birth in the second trimester.

b) Describe the **challenge cohort**, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

Cervical screening of pregnant women to prevent preterm birth.

Item 17: Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the **imaging technique(s)** applied in the challenge.

2D ultrasound imaging

Item 18: Context information

Provide additional **information given along with the images**. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the **image data** (e.g. tumor volume).

These images will include cervix anatomical structures (the anterior lip and posterior lip of the cervix).

b) ... to the **patient** in general (e.g. gender, medical history).

Pregnant women with a variety of age.

Item 19: Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the **data origin**, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Anterior lip and posterior lip are shown in ultrasound images.

b) Describe the **algorithm target**, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Participants have to submit a Docker image that can segment anterior lip and posterior lip.

Item 20: Assessment aim(s)

Identify the **property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized** to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (parameter 26), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- *Example 1:* Find liver segmentation algorithm for CT images that processes CT images of a certain size in less than a minute on a certain hardware with an error that reflects inter-rater variability of experts.
- *Example 2:* Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter 26).

CHALLENGE DATA SETS

Item 21: Data source(s)

a) Specify the **device(s)** used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

Images were acquired from a total of seven different US machines by several different operators with similar experience. US machines were Voluson E6, Voluson S8 and Voluson S10 (GE Medical Systems, Zipf, Austria), Aloka (Aloka CO., LTD.), Mindray DC-N2 (Shenzhen Mindray Bio-Medical Electronics Co., Ltd, China/Germany), ACUSON X600 (Siemens), and EDAN DUS 60 (Edan Instruments, Inc., Shenzhen, China).

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/**data acquisition** for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

Transvaginal ultrasounds of the uterine cervix were recorded after bladder emptying. Women were positioned in a low Fowler's position during the scan. Women were asked to empty their bladder immediately before the examination. Images were taken using a curved transducer with a frequency range from a 2 to 10-MHz vaginal probe (used for cervical US screening in second trimester patients). Operators were instructed to avoid using any type of post-processing or artifacts such as smoothing, noise, pointers or calipers when possible. The remaining image settings parameters such as gain, frequency and gain compensation were left to their discretion.

c) Specify the **center(s)/institute(s)** in which the data was acquired and/or the **data providing platform/source** (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

(1) Hospital Clínic and Hospital Sant Joan de Deu, Barcelona, Spain
(2) Maternal and Fetal Medicine Unit, Vall d'Hebron Hospital Universitari, Barcelona, Spain
(3) Queen Elizabeth Central Hospital, Malawi
(4) Sayedaty Center, Egypt
(5) Mulago National Referral Hospital, Uganda
(6) KBTH Polyclinic (Accra), Ghana
(7) EPH Kouba and Clinique Des Lilas, Algeria

d) Describe relevant **characteristics** (e.g. level of expertise) **of the subjects** (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Data annotation is overseen by the challenge clinical chair Gaowen Chen. He is an experienced radiologist with more than seven years professional experience.

Item 22: Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one **case** in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in *data*

source(s) (parameter 21) and may include context information (parameter 18). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

One case, in this challenge, is a single US image associated with/withoug a three-class segmentation mask.

b) State the **total number** of training, validation and test cases.

The total number of cases is 890. There are 500/90/300 cases for training, validation, and testing, respectively. In the training set, 50 cases have three-class annotations (background, the anterior lip and posterior lip), and the remaining 450 cases are unlabeled.

c) Explain **why a total number** of cases and **the specific proportion** of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The challenge is designed for benchmarking semi-supervised learning methods. Thus, only a small set of cases are labeled and a large number of unlabeled cases can be used for training.

d) Mention **further important characteristics** of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

All the testing cases will be hidden to participants and the Docker container will be used for submission. Importantly, none of labels are publicly available in the testing set.

Item 23: Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the **method for determining the reference annotation**, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include *manual image annotation*, *in silico ground truth generation* and *annotation by automatic methods*. If human annotation was involved, state the **number of annotators**.

Anterior lip and posterior lip were annotated with the strategy of automatic segmentation and manual correction. There are six annotators and radiologists.

b) Provide the **instructions given to the annotators** (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the **annotation protocol**.

Annotators and radiologists were asked to use Pair software.

c) Provide **details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated** the cases (e.g. information on **level of expertise** such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

We employed a hierarchical and human-in-the-loop strategy to annotate the organs.

d) Describe the **method(s) used to merge multiple annotations** for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

An experienced radiologist finally check and revise all the annotations.

Item 24: Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the **method(s) used for pre-processing** the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Participants should develop their own pre-processing methods.

Item 25: Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant **possible error sources related to the image annotation**. If possible, **estimate the magnitude** (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Error is unavoidable in medical image segmentation. We will have a github repository to collect feedbacks from participants about possible errors that they discover in the dataset. This strategy was also used in MICCAI PSFHS and IUGC.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify **other relevant sources of error**.

None.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Item 26: Metric(s)

a) Define the **metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm**. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in *assessment aim(s)* (parameter 20). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- *Example 1*: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC) and run-time
- *Example 2*: Area under curve (AUC)

Dice Similarity Coefficient, Hausdorff Distance, Running time

b) **Justify why** the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

All metrics will be used to compute the ranking.

Item 27: Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the **method used to compute a performance rank** for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

The three metrics are complementary. Specifically, Dice Similarity Coefficient is used to measure the region error. Hausdorff Distance is used to measure the boundary error. Running time is used to measure the inference speed.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage **submissions with missing results** on test cases.

Missing results on test cases will result in the ranks being set to the maximum (the number of teams). Specifically, missing results will get a zero value for Dice Similarity Coefficient, and the equivalent worst value for Hausdorff Distance, and running time.

c) **Justify why** the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

The main benefit of this ranking scheme is that it can aggregate the metrics with different dimensions. A similar ranking scheme was also employed in MICCAI Challenge 2023-2024.

Item 28: Statistical analyses

a) Provide **details for the statistical methods** used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the **missing data handling**,

- details about the assessment of **variability of rankings**,
- description of any method used to assess **whether the data met the assumptions**, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any **software product** that was used for all data analysis methods.

Ranking variability will be characterized using the bootstrap.

b) **Justify why** the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

The Bootstrap is a simple nonparametric method that relies on minimal assumptions.

Item 29: Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- **combining algorithms** via ensembling,
- **inter-algorithm variability**,
- **common problems/biases** of the submitted methods, or
- **ranking variability**.

Inter-algorithm variability and Common problems/biases of the submitted methods.

